

Change Management

A hybrid approach to successfully implement change processes

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Abstract

To minimize resistance to change processes, a hybrid approach based on the change management models of Kotter and Hiatt is presented. The hybrid model considers organizational structures and employee needs and can be used flexibly.

Keywords Change management, hybrid approach, Kotter, AKDAR

Introduction

When introducing changes, you always encounter resistance. To counteract this, a holistic and flexible approach is needed that considers both organizational structures and the needs of the employees involved.

A combination of the change management model of Kotter (2011) and the AKDAR model of Hiatt (2006) can be considered as a suitable approach. The hybrid approach proposed here combines the strengths of both models and promises a structured yet adaptable strategy for the successful implementation of change.

Kotter & AKDAR Model

Kotter (2011) describes eight defined steps that aim to initiate, implement and anchor an organizational change in the long term. The eight steps include creating a sense of urgency, building a leadership coalition, developing and communicating a vision, removing obstacles, achieving short-term successes, consolidating profits, and embedding the changes in the company's culture (Kotter, 2011). The model ensures that change is strategically anchored and underpinned by strong leadership and an unobstructed vision.

The ADKAR model expands the organizational steps to include a focus on the individual change processes of employees (Hiatt & Creasey, 2012) and comprises five phases: creating awareness of the need for change, awakening the desire to support the change, imparting the necessary knowledge to implement the change, developing the ability to implement the change and consolidating change through continuous reinforcement (Hiatt, 2006). The model ensures that the individual needs and abilities of employees are taken into account and promoted.

Hybrid approach

A combination of the two models in five phases, as shown in Figure 1, provides a comprehensive approach and allows the integration of the strategic and structural elements of Kotter with the individual and behavioral aspects of the ADKAR model. Another advantage of this hybrid approach is the flexibility and adaptability. While the Kotter model provides clear step-by-step guidance on how to implement the change at the organizational level, the ADKAR model allows for customization to the specific needs and responses of each employee. This is particularly relevant in an interdisciplinary team environment,

where the dynamics and requirements can be diverse and complex.

Example

At X-Pharma, a fictional pharmaceutical company, communication issues and lack of engagement lead to inefficient prioritization of tasks and production delays. The goal is to develop a training program that strengthens the emotional intelligence of team members and thus improves communication processes as well as team cohesion. The following description of the phases is based on the work of Kotter (2011) and Hiatt and Creasey (2012).

Phase 1

The first phase is to create urgency by informing the area managers and the HR department about the critical

situation and the possible negative impact on the company's production and reputation. This creates awareness of the need for a quick and effective solution.

A leadership coalition is then formed consisting of the HR department, the division managers and the line managers. The concept will be presented and coordinated with the leadership coalition to reach a consensus and approve the planned measures. Based on the concept, a vision and strategy for implementation are developed so that the challenges can be met, and emotional intelligence can be promoted.

Phase 2

In the second phase of implementation, it is crucial that all affected team members are comprehensively informed about the planned measure and

Figure 1:

Hybrid Changemanagement-Model

Note. Presentation based on Hiatt (2006, p. 2) and Kotter (2011, p. 18).

its necessity. Effective communication of the vision helps to increase employee engagement and motivation. At the same time, awareness of the necessity of change is created by showing the reasons and the expected positive effects for employees.

The personal benefits for the team members are highlighted, such as improving communication skills, strengthening team cohesion, increasing job satisfaction and reducing conflicts. These aspects illustrate how fostering emotional intelligence can lead to better interpersonal relationships and more effective collaboration.

Phase 3

Implementation in Phase 3 involves several steps, starting with empowering employees to implement the changes through training and providing the necessary resources. In addition to training, knowledge is imparted through team and individual coaching to ensure that employees acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. These are applied in practice and consolidated through continuous feedback.

Phase 4

In the fourth phase of the change process, the realization of short-term successes takes place as a further part of the process. Improvements in the performance of the teams are communicated and celebrated through a joint event, such as a dinner, once measurable successes have been achieved. This motivates employees and shows that change is possible. To consolidate the successes achieved and initiate further changes, suitable key performance indicators (KPIs) are used. These enable continuous monitoring and evaluation of progress. Regular quarterly reflections of the KPIs and jointly developed measures for further improvement ensure that the changes are intensified and sustainable.

Phase 5

Sustainability and anchoring the change in the team culture are the final steps in phase 5. Through constant measurement with the KPIs after the introduction of the change measures and improvement measures derived from them, the change is to be anchored in the team culture. Adapting team culture and behaviors is important to support the new practices in the long term and ensure that the changes remain sustainable and successful (Hiatt & Creasey, 2012; Kotter, 2011).

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